

ESTIMATION OF IONOSPHERIC PARAMETERS AT THE UKRAINIAN ANTARCTIC AKADEMIK VERNADSKY STATION USING MACHINE LEARNING

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At the Ukrainian Antarctic Akademik Vernadsky station (UAS), both a classical ionosonde (IPS-42) and an SDR-based ionosonde operate concurrently, generating ionograms at 15-minute intervals. The standard geophysical data processing protocol at the UAS involves manual scaling of ionograms recorded every hour. However, studying ionospheric dynamics – particularly during geomagnetic storms – requires scaling all ionograms within the event and reference periods. Given that manual scaling is labor-intensive and time-consuming, automating this process is highly relevant. Moreover, automatic scaling enables real-time data processing, which is essential for integrating ionospheric observations into international space weather services.

This paper presents a novel technique and accompanying software for automatic ionogram scaling. The study employs machine learning methodologies, specifically artificial neural networks (ANNs) with a U-Net architecture, to detect F2 O- and X-traces in ionograms. The developed software utilizes two such ANNs to enhance trace recognition accuracy. An earlier prototype of the ANN (Bogomaz et al., 2020) was capable of identifying F2 O-traces in ionograms obtained using the IPS-42 ionosonde. The current iteration incorporates several key advancements, including an increased resolution of both input and output layers, a substantially larger training dataset, and refined preprocessing algorithms. These improvements enhance the model’s performance for ionogram analysis for multiple ionosondes operating at the UAS, optimizing both input data handling and image segmentation results.

The software was developed in Python using the TensorFlow and Keras. Ionogram preprocessing is conducted with NumPy, Pillow, OpenCV-Python, and SciPy, while post-processing of recognition results is performed using OpenCV-Python routines.

To evaluate the accuracy of F2-layer critical frequency (foF2) estimations generated by the ANN-based software, manually scaled hourly values for 2023, recorded during the 27th and 28th Ukrainian Antarctic expeditions, were used as a reference dataset. Approximately 50% of the foF2 estimates generated by the ANN deviate from the manually scaled values by no more than ± 0.1 MHz.

A script for real-time foF2 estimation runs on a virtual machine hosted on the UAS server and uploads the results, stored in JSON files, to cloud storage within 4 seconds after the completion of each ionospheric sounding session.

Bogomaz, O., Shulha, M., Kotov, D., Koloskov, A., & Zalizovski, A. (2020). An artificial neural network for analysis of ionograms obtained by ionosonde at the Ukrainian Antarctic Akademik Vernadsky station. *Ukrainian Antarctic Journal*, (2), 59–67.